

The BAM Data Store

Establishing an openBIS-Based Research Data Infrastructure in Materials Science and Engineering

Angela Ariza¹ <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-0912-8137>,
José Pizarro³ <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-8935-6059>

¹ Bundesanstalt für Materialforschung und -prüfung, Germany

Abstract

With more than 1,000 scientific employees, the Federal Institute for Materials Research and Testing (BAM) conducts research, development, and technical services with high societal relevance [1]. By participating in several NFDI consortia and digitization projects that contribute to the standardization of Materials Science and Engineering (MSE) related (meta-)data, BAM is actively shaping the future of Research Data Management (RDM) [2], [3], [4].

As part of its institutional strategy to implement the FAIR data principles [5] and to support researchers in the day-to-day management of research data. The eScience and IT sections work together to establish a centralized RDM platform—the BAM Data Store. This platform is based on the open-source framework openBIS [6], [7], developed, and maintained by the Scientific IT Services of ETH Zurich in close collaboration with an active user community that includes several large institutions from MSE-related disciplines.

The BAM Data Store project, active since 2021, aims to provide institution-wide services for infrastructure, training, and the definition of metadata standards. This contribution builds on insights shared at CoRDI-2023 [8] to provide an update on the institutional rollout of the system and highlight the strategies used to address challenges posed by BAM's scale and disciplinary diversity. Key topics include the challenges of establishing a centralized RDM platform in a large, multidisciplinary organization, and the strategies used to ensure scalability, user acceptance, and sustainability. A particular focus is on the role of Data Store Stewards (DSSs)—researchers embedded in scientific groups who support the implementation and act as multipliers. Their engagement emphasizes the need to recognize RDM-related contributions as part of scientific output.

From a technical and structural perspective, the Data Store leverages the flexible, entity-based data model of openBIS to represent heterogeneous MSE workflows. However, this agnosticism requires the development of harmonized, semantically enriched metadata schemas to ensure interoperability across the institution and beyond. Our ongoing efforts to define a generic yet extensible metadata model for MSE disciplines aim to connect institutional RDM practice with national and international standards.

By presenting the BAM Data Store project, we contribute practical insights and implementation strategies for institutions facing similar challenges in infrastructure development, role definition, and metadata interoperability.

Keywords: FAIR, Interoperability, Institutional RDM, openBIS, Material Science and Engineering, Electronic lab notebook, Training, Infrastructure.

Resources

No new data was created or analyzed. Therefore, there is no need to archive material in a repository.

Author contributions

Angela Ariza: Methodology (lead); conceptualization (equal); writing – original draft (lead); writing – review and editing (equal); visualization (lead). Philipp Benner: Supervision (lead); project administration (lead); conceptualization (equal); writing – review and editing (equal). José Pizarro: Methodology (supporting); writing – original draft (supporting); writing – review and editing (equal). Jörg Rädler: project administration (lead); Software (lead); conceptualization (equal); writing – original draft (supporting); writing – review and editing (equal).

Competing interests

The authors declare that they have no competing interests.

Funding

The BAM Data Store project is funded by internal BAM resources.

Acknowledgement

If you want to acknowledge persons or institutions you can do so here.

References

- [1] „The Federal Institute of Materials Research and Testing (BAM) – 150 Years of Enabling Scientific and Technological Breakthrough“. *Advanced Engineering Materials* 24, Nr. 6 (Juni 2022): 2200648. <https://doi.org/10.1002/adem.202200648>.
- [2] Ávila Calderón, L.A., Y. Shakeel, A. Gedsun, M. Forti, S. Hunke, Y. Han, T. Hammerschmidt, u. a. „Management of Reference Data in Materials Science and Engineering Exemplified for Creep Data of a Single-Crystalline Ni-Based Superalloy“. *Acta Materialia* 286 (März 2025): 120735. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.actamat.2025.120735>.
- [3] Rejiba, Khalil, Prince Mathews, Niklas Siemer, Ulrich Kerzel, Pavlina Kruzikova, Ujjal Saikia, Ost Philipp, Sandra Korte-Kerzel, und Tilmann Hickel. „IUC04: Towards Semi Automated Construction of Defect Phase Diagrams“. Zenodo, 5. August 2024. <https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.13220179>.
- [4] Rejiba, Khalil, Niklas Siemer, Pavlína Kružiková, Tarakeshwar Lakshminpathy, Tilmann Hickel, und Ulrich Kerzel. „Digital Materials Science Lab - RDM and Workflows“, 14. April 2025. <https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.15209702>.
- [5] Wilkinson, Mark D., Michel Dumontier, IJsbrand Jan Aalbersberg, Gabrielle Appleton, Myles Axton, Arie Baak, Niklas Blomberg, u. a. „The FAIR Guiding Principles for Scientific Data Management and Stewardship“. *Scientific Data* 3, Nr. 1 (15. März 2016): 160018. <https://doi.org/10.1038/sdata.2016.18>.
- [6] Bauch, Angela, Izabela Adamczyk, Piotr Buczek, Franz-Josef Elmer, Kaloyan Enimanev, Pawel Glyzowski, Manuel Kohler, u. a. „openBIS: a flexible framework for managing and

- analyzing complex data in biology research". *BMC Bioinformatics* 12, Nr. 1 (8. Dezember 2011): 468. <https://doi.org/10.1186/1471-2105-12-468>.
- [7] Barillari, Caterina, Diana S. M. Ottoz, Juan Mariano Fuentes-Serna, Chandrasekhar Ramakrishnan, Bernd Rinn, und Fabian Rudolf. „openBIS ELN-LIMS: an open-source database for academic laboratories“. *Bioinformatics* 32, Nr. 4 (15. Februar 2016): 638–40. <https://doi.org/10.1093/bioinformatics/btv606>.
- [8] El-Athman, Rukeia, Jörg Rädler, Oliver Löhmann, Angela Ariza de Schellenberger, und Thilo Muth. „The BAM Data Store: Piloting an openBIS-Based Research Data Infrastructure for Materials Science and Engineering“, 19. September 2023. <https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.8359945>.